

FINANCIAL TECHNOLOGY (FINTECH) AND FINANCIAL SERVICE DELIVERY OF DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Financial technology (FinTech) continues to transform and influence the Nigerian financial sector. In recent years, the banking industry in Nigeria has increasingly emphasized mobile banking and internet banking as strategic tools for cost reduction and profit enhancement. However, the extent to which FinTech contributes to the growth of Nigeria's financial sector remains a critical issue. This study therefore examines the impact of financial technology on financial service delivery by deposit money banks and its effect on the growth of the Nigerian financial sector from 2012 to 2024. The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was employed to analyze both the short-run and long-run relationships among the variables. Prior to estimation, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test was conducted to determine the stationarity properties of the data. Additional diagnostic tests were also carried out to validate the robustness of the results. The findings revealed that FinTech has a significant and positive effect on financial service delivery among Nigerian deposit money banks. Furthermore, FinTech was found to significantly influence Nigeria's economic growth. Based on these findings, the study recommends that bank managers enhance the efficiency and usability of mobile, internet, and point-of-sale platforms, while policymakers should create an enabling environment that promotes the adoption and effective use of financial technology to support financial sector development and economic growth in Nigeria.*

1.1 Introduction

Financial technology has made enormous strides recently for financial institutions. Their operations and the adoption of technology have

produced seamless operations. Financial technology is being adopted and used by banks as well (Adiga, Adigwe, Okonkwo & Ogbonna, 2022). Financial technology is the

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modernization of financial services by businesses or their representatives using cutting-edge technology (Dorfletner, Hornuf, Schmitt & Weber, 2017). Financial technology made Fintech possible (FinTech Weekly, 2016). It was declared that the use of financial technologies knew no industry boundaries because it enhanced information dissemination, increased service delivery efficiency, and increased transparency and accountability (Shailendra, 2020). Deposit and withdrawal processes, clearing and settlement, credit processing, online account statements, account opening, funds transfers, capital raising, and card services are all aided by Fintech in banking operations. It also makes staff records, evaluation processes, and auditing possible. Financial technology helps banks in many ways, including quick service delivery, customer convenience, higher profitability, and increased market share.

The commercial banks (DMBs) in Nigeria's banking sector made significant investments in IT goods and services. About 70% of the industry's total investment cost and 46% of organizational information technology spending in Nigeria are accounted for by DMB's FinTech investments (CBN, 2009). High capital expenditures and deliberate commitments are essential for FinTech success. Private very-small-aperture terminals (VSAT) were constructed by DMBs to address Nigeria's communication infrastructure (Agboola & Salawu, 2008; Andoh-Baidoo & Osatuyi, 2009). DMBs in Nigeria spent \$114 million on

IT each year (Ayankotun, 2008). The 24 commercial banks in the nation invested more than \$107 million in IT and related services in 2009 (Ekata, 2011). Due to an increase in electronic fraud from 2018 to 2020, this increased (Ogbonna, Okaro & Igwe, 2019).

However, over the past few decades, the global banking sector has undergone a significant amount of change (Nejad, 2016). Financial technology, or FinTech, has long played a significant role in the economy. FinTech is crucial for allocating funds to useful uses, distributing risk to those who can benefit from it, and accelerating financial development. Failure to adopt FinTech results in the exclusion of many households from traditional banking systems, which in turn causes sluggish financial development and, ultimately, slow economic growth (Neaime & Gaysset, 2018). Financial technology has significantly influenced how financial institutions operate and has helped lay the groundwork for financial institutions to differentiate themselves in a crowded market (Cihak & Singh, 2013). In light of this, this study investigates the effects of financial technology (FinTech) on deposit money banks' ability to deliver financial services as well as Nigeria's financial development.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The Central Bank's cashless policy, which was implemented in 2012 with the goal of reducing the quantity of cash in circulation while promoting the use of electronic payments, has historically been the driving force behind the

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recent boom in FinTech in Nigeria. Furthermore, the covid-19 pandemic has compelled many firms to develop virtual channels of communication with their clients. Thus, using digital technology is the only method to make transactions by proxy function today. So, in order to survive and remain competitive, local banking systems had no alternative but to adapt and embrace FinTech-based cashless methods of serving their consumers.

There is a growing need for new kinds of investments as a result of the integration and globalization of financial markets. The threat of existing to deposit taking in financial institutions is caused by the ability to innovate and the financial innovation and its effects, which have emerged as the key component. The growth of the company is significantly influenced by financial performance. Financial innovation is also influenced by changes in the global financial environment, the expansion of international financial markets, and the merger of domestic financial markets. To handle the massive amounts of money they transact each day, local financial institution like commercial banks have been obliged to adapt to new financial technologies. They have kept up the innovation and improved customer service by launching new products, new financial institution services, and calling for changes in the tactics of regulatory bodies. Despite all of these breakthroughs, the financial sector has not yet fully realized the impact that innovation has on financial institution growth. This can be

a result of a lack of knowledge about the forces driving innovation and the sluggish evaluation of bank performance (Mabrouk & Mamoghli, 2010). The latest financial crisis affecting the entire world has its roots in banks and other financial intermediaries.

One of the primary structural causes of the crisis was the decline in their asset portfolios, which was mostly brought on by faulty credit management (Steven, 2002). Commercial banks must be managed successfully and economically by continuously pursuing financial innovations due to the rapidly shifting competitive environment, globalization, economic changes, regulation, privatization, and similar factors. Any commercial bank in Nigeria is required to employ the necessary skills to maintain competitiveness and gain a competitive edge due to the advent of new technology, products, processes, markets, and competitor banks. The banking sector has already been characterized as having minimal market orientation, providing services with little consideration for consumer needs, and having branches with varying levels of efficiency, all of which have contributed to poor financial performance (Parasuman, 2001). Nonetheless, it has been reported that the most common issues with using financial services are lengthy lines, transaction mistakes, queuing, security issues, and network outages (Smith, 1999). This significantly lowers customers' perceptions of the level of service provided, which lowers the bank's trustworthiness and ultimately its profitability (Joseph, et al.,

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2003). In order to better understand how financial technology (FinTech) affects Nigeria's financial development and deposit money banks' capacity to provide financial services.

This study aims to provide a scholarly contribution to the knowledge in the area of relationship between financial technology (FinTech) and financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2012 – 2024. The objective of the study is:

1. To determine the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria.
2. To examine the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial development in Nigeria.

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Framework

According to Freytag and Fricke (2017), financial technology is cutting-edge technology that supports financial services. In order to provide innovative financial goods and services that can reach a wider range of entities, including both corporate and individual clients, FinTech refers to businesses that base their financial services on a reliable technological platform (Mlanga, 2019). FinTech has gained traction because startup businesses using it to enter the market are trying to disrupt the way

things are done traditionally by utilizing cutting-edge technical channels in areas like asset management and money transfer (Truong, 2016). One amazing aspect of FinTech is its capacity to maintain market efficiency while keeping transaction costs to an absolute minimum.

In other cases, the term "financial service" refers to the economic service offered by the finance industry, which consists of numerous entities engaged in the business of managing money (Irena, 2020). Financial services only refer to official financial services. Services including saving, credit, payments, investments, insurance, and pensions are covered under the umbrella of general financial services. Financial services are therefore conceptualized in two ways in the development finance literature. The way financial services are conceptualized may only pay attention to formal financial institutions' goods, leaving out the financial operations of the informal sector. These includes items that allow people to make deposits, withdraw money, get credit, buy insurance, and use money transfer services (Allen, Demirgüç-Kunt, Klapper, & Pera, 2016). The figure 2.1 showed the conceptual model of this study.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Model

Source: Researcher Computation 2026

Figure 2.1 above illustrates how to conceptualize how variables should be related to one another. The predictor variable will be financial technology, which is defined according to Chiomba (2021) as banking innovation including the internet, mobile devices, agencies, and ATMs. The control variables will be changes in interest rates and economic expansion. The deposit money held by banks, along with the amount of private sector credit, will be the dependent variables used to measure financial development.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

The innovation theories are the main hypotheses supporting the emergence of FinTech. In this part of the investigation, these theories will be taken into account.

a. Innovator's Solution Theory

According to Christensen and Taylor (1997), who were quoted by Kariuki (2010), the main reason businesses fail is a lack of innovation. This analysis led to the advancement of the theory. The theory's main argument is that large corporations are not as motivated to address the issue of disruptive innovation since such concepts could pose a danger to management, the system of power, and

corporate culture. As a result, established forces in markets and businesses often oppose innovation that could occur from FinTech. The proponents of this approach, however, rely on business management to build a barrier between impending innovation and the current hierarchy and structure. In this situation, a stand-alone company unit could be created to offer a secure environment for innovation (Kariuki, 2010).

b. Disruptive Innovation Theory

According to this thesis, which was put forth by Christensen in 1997, innovation is the best way to get a competitive advantage in a world that is always changing. Disruptive innovation boosts the growth of any firm and establishes a new trend in the market, even though innovation raises the rate of uncertainty and market pressure. As a result, the more radical the type of innovation, the harder it is to readily decide on its market acceptability. These theories illustrated how organizations use new technologies to gain a competitive edge. Essentially, how POS transactions, internet banking, and mobile payments are used for efficient financial services.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Since 2005, there has been a lot of interest in financial technology, and both advanced and developing nations have conducted extensive research. Ashiru, Balogun, and Paseda (2023) evaluated how mobile, internet, and ATMs affected banks' financial performance from 2012 to 2021. All 24 Nigerian deposit money banks were studied. The ARDL model research

shows that POS banking service has the strongest impact on deposit money bank performance due to the high quantity and value of banking transactions. Hence, online and mobile banking should be expanded. ATMs, mobile banking, credit and debit cards, online banking, and agency banking have a beneficial short- and long-term impact on deposit money banks in Nigeria, except for National Electronic Fund Transfer (NEFT) and NIBSS Instant Payments (NIP). Muhammad, Abdulmalik, and Halima (2022) examined how financial technology (FinTech) affects Nigerian deposit money banks' financial services from 2012 to 2021, using the banks' annual reports and accounts. Descriptive statistics, correlation, and regression examine data. Mobile, online, and POS banking have greatly affected Nigeria's listed deposit money banks' financial services.

Adiga, et al., (2022) examined Nigeria's banking and financial technology. Analysis employed Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL). Financial technology explained DMBs' return on assets, equity, and non-interest income, except for interest income. Financial technology strongly explained the banking sector's performance components of return on assets, return on equity, and non-interest income. Although the relationship between the two variables was equivocal, financial technology did not improve or improve the banking industry over the study period. Nwarisi, Igwe, and Ozuru (2022) examined how digital service delivery affects Nigerian deposit money institutions' finances. Study

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design was explanatory. As they're all in Rivers State, the Nigeria Stock Exchange's 14 listed deposit money institutions had 14 people. Yet, 140 people—10 from each of the 14 banks would provide our cross-sectional data. Multiple regression and structural equation modeling were employed. The study found a considerable and negligible association between digital service delivery and corporate success. The study found that digital service delivery can boost or hurt corporate success.

Mohammed, Ibrahim, and Muritala (2022) used the Auto-Regressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) limitations approach to co-integration on quarterly time-series data from Q1 2007 to Q4 2020 to examine how payments system improvements affected Nigerian commercial banks. RTGS negatively affected Nigerian commercial banks' return on assets, while mobile payment, POS transactions, and internet payment had positive and significant effects. Gbanador, Makwe, and Oladele (2022) examined how financial innovation affects Nigeria's deposit money institutions using 2009–2021 data. Point of sale, ATM, internet, and mobile banking were independent factors, and deposit money banks' assets were dependent variables. The ARDL model analyzed. POS outperformed internet banking.

Oyetoyan and Ajiboye (2021) examined how FinTech regulation affected Deposit Money Banks in Kwara State, Nigeria, institutions. Quantitative methods collected and analyzed data. 220 employees from five Deposit Money Banks were selected in Ilorin. So, using a well-

structured questionnaire, banks provided ethical behavior data in the FinTech service regulatory framework. Participants were institution managers and executives. Multiple regression, ANOVA, and Pearson Moment Correlation tested the hypothesis. PayStack, Branch, PiggyVest, Mines, and NetPlus positively affect deposit money banks, according to the study. Nigerian banks' performance also depends on digital innovation regulation. Oyetoyan and Ajiboye (2021) found that FinTech services boost efficiency and social structure in a secure network. Bank performance improved. Wachira, Kalui, and Gathii (2021) used multiple regression and Pearson correlations. The study demonstrated negative relationship between mobile money that is, registered accounts, active agents, and deposits and withdrawals, digital payments (P2P transfers), and commercial bank performance in Kenya. The study found a high positive association between client deposits, gross non-performing loans, and Kenyan commercial banks' performance. Wachira, et al., (2021) concluded that Fintech startups' digital financial services hurt Kenyan commercial banks.

The goal of this study was to fill in any gaps in the body of knowledge regarding the relationship between financial technology (FinTech) and the provision of financial services by Nigerian deposit money banks. The literature review revealed that current studies have primarily focused on financial technology (FinTech) and the provision of financial

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services by deposit money banks without considering the impact of FinTech on the provision of financial services by DMBs and financial development over the period of 2012 to 2024. This research would aid in bridging the empirical gap.

3.0 Research Methods

3.1 Model Specification

To comprehend and verify the links between two or more variables, economic models are created. It compels a researcher to consider a problem's key interrelationships and take them into account (Pindyck & Rubinfeld, 1997). Economic theories are typically the foundation of economic modelling. Hence, knowledge of economic theory as well as the results of related investigations on the phenomenon being studied is required for the specification of economic models (Koutsoyannis, 1977). This study examines how deposit money banks in Nigeria perform financial services in connection to financial technology (FinTech).

3.1.1 Objective 1: To determine the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria

The model that was used for this investigation was developed from a prior study that had been carried out by Adiga, et al., (2022), with certain modifications made to it. This was done in order to accomplish the aims of the study. The following is a specification of the functional form of the model as a result:

$$DMBs = f(OT, POS, MBT, ATM, LR, GDPG) \quad (1)$$

The econometric estimation form of the functional specification of model above is presented as follows:

$$DMBs = \beta + \beta_1OT + \beta_2POS + \beta_3ATM + \beta_4MBT + \beta_5LR + \beta_6GDPG + \mu \quad (2)$$

However, in order to reduce the problem of spurious regression in the analysis, log linear model was adopted. The model can be stated thus:

$$\ln DMBS = \beta + \beta_1 \ln OT + \beta_2 \ln POS + \beta_3 \ln ATM + \beta_4 \ln MBT + \beta_5 \ln LR + \beta_6 \ln GDPG + \mu \quad (3)$$

Where:

LnDMBS = Log of Deposit Money Banks Assets

LnOT = Log of Online Transactions

LnPOS = Log of Point of Sale Transactions

LnATM = Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions

LnMBT = Log of Mobile Banking Transactions

LR = Lending rate

GPDG = GDP Growth rate

β_0 is the intercept

β_1 to β_6 represents the slope coefficients

μ is the stochastic term or the error term.

A *prior* expectation = $\beta_1 - \beta_4 > 0$, while $\beta_5, \beta_6 < 0$,

3.1.2. Objective 2: To examine the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial development in Nigeria.

This research work adapted and modified the study of Ashiru, et al., (2023). The functional form of the model used in this study is specified as follows:

$$PCS = f(OT, POS, MBT, ATM, LR, GDPG) \quad (4)$$

The econometric estimation form of the functional specification of model above is presented as follows:

$$PSC = \alpha + \alpha_1 OT + \alpha_2 POS + \alpha_3 ATM + \alpha_4 MBT + \alpha_5 LR + \alpha_6 GDPG + \mu \quad (5)$$

However, in order to reduce the problem of spurious regression in the analysis, log linear model was adopted. The model can be stated thus:

$$PSC = \alpha + \alpha_1 \ln OT + \alpha_2 \ln POS + \alpha_3 \ln ATM + \alpha_4 \ln MBT + \alpha_5 \ln LR + \alpha_6 \ln GDPG + \mu \quad (6)$$

Where:

PSC = Private sector credit (% GDP)

LnOT = Log of Online Transactions

LnPOS = Log of Point of Sale Transactions

LnATM = Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions

LnMBT = Log of Mobile Banking Transactions

LR = Lending rate

GPDG = GDP Growth rate

α_0 is the intercept

α_1 to α_6 represents the slope coefficients

μ is the stochastic term or the error term.

A *prior* expectation = $\alpha_1 - \alpha_4 > 0$, while α_5 , $\alpha_6 < 0$,

3.2 Method of Analysis

A pretest for stationarity of variables is important to prevent erroneous regression (Osuala, 2010). Hence, it's probable that a lot of the series you would have assumed were stationary based on the ARDL model regression was actually generated by random walks (Cochrane, 2005). All the variables must undergo a unit root test using the Gujarati-recommended Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)

test. The Akaike information criteria will decide which lag to use. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test was used to evaluate the unit root test. In addition, the analysis used Pesaran, et al., (2001) Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds co-integration technique. The study used primarily secondary data from the years 2012 through 2024. The Central Bank of Nigeria Statistics Bulletin was used as the source for the data sets. Given its usability and dependability, E-Views 13 was used to estimate the model.

4.0 Presentation and Analysis of Results

4.1 Unit Root Test Results

In a research involving the use of time series data, it is ideal to carry out stationarity tests on the series to be used. This is justified on the grounds that data not found stationary has the tendency of yielding spurious regression results and thus misleading policy projections. If a unit root exists in any variable, then that particular series is considered to be non-stationary. This becomes necessary as put by Granger and Newbold (1974), and Granger (1986) that if time series variables are non-stationary, all findings with these time series will be at variance with the conventional theory of regression with stationary series. Estimation based on non-stationary variables may lead to spurious results with high R^2 explains how much of the variances in the dependent variable is accounted for by the regression model from the sample) and t-statistics, but without any coherent economic meaning and inconsistent parameter estimator (Pindyck &

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Rubinfeld, 1997). The stationary test was performed to avoid spurious regression problems normally associated with time series econometric modeling. The Augmented Dickey

Fuller (ADF) test for estimating unit roots was applied in this study. The result of ADF testing can be seen in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Abridged ADF Unit Root Test for the Models Respectively

	Variables	ADF-Statistic	Critical Value @ 5%	Order of Int.
Model 1	Log of Deposit Money Banks Assets (LnDMBS)	-4.479744	-3.403313	1(1)
	Log of Online Transactions (LnOT)	-5.425758	-3.259808	1(0)
	Log of Point of Sale Transactions (LnPOS)	-4.682219	-3.259808	1(0)
	Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions (LnATM)	-3.867528	-3.403313	1(1)
	Log of Mobile Banking Transactions (LnMBT)	-4.278908	-3.320969	1(1)
	Lending rate (LR)	-4.532438	-3.320969	1(0)
	GDP Growth rate (GDPG)	-5.821033	-3.259808	1(0)
Model 2	Private sector credit (PSC)	-5.475912	-3.320969	1(0)
	Log of Online Transactions (LnOT)	-5.425758	-3.259808	1(0)
	Log of Point of Sale Transactions (LnPOS)	-4.682219	-3.259808	1(0)
	Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions (LnATM)	-3.867528	-3.403313	1(1)
	Log of Mobile Banking Transactions (LnMBT)	-4.278908	-3.320969	1(1)
	Lending rate (LR)	-4.532438	-3.320969	1(0)

	GDP Growth rate (GDPG)	-5.821033	-3.259808	1(0)
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Source: Author's Compilation using E-views 13Output

Time series data are always associated with the problem of non-stationarity. This could decrease the validity of forecast based on such data. In order to overcome this problem, this study used the standard Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests to examine the stationarity or otherwise of the data in this study. Consequently, the results of the estimated Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests shown in the above table clearly indicate that data on the variables such as Log of Online Transactions (LnOT), Log of Point of Sale Transactions (LnPOS), Lending rate (LR), GDP Growth rate (GDPG) and Private sector credit (PSC) are stationary at level 1(0) based on 5 percent level of significance in the models respectively. While the Log of Deposit Money Banks Assets (LnDMBS), Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions (LnATM) and Log of Mobile Banking Transactions (LnMBT) were stationary at first differences 1(1) in the models respectively. This suggested that the variables were integrated of order 1(0) and 1(1). Based on the ADF test the condition for Johansen cointegration test is not met. This kind of conflict between the outcomes of the two tests is common in practice (Shahbaz & Rahman,

2012). According to Ouattara (2004), the bounds test approach is valid only when the variables are a mix of I (0) and I (1). Therefore, we can safely go ahead with the bounds test. Owing to this, the study investigates the long-run relationship between the variables concerned by employing an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) method. This approach is applied to time series data characterized with different orders of integration (a mixture of I(0) and I(1)).

4.2 ARDL Bounds Testing Procedure

The ARDL bound testing procedure is used to check if a long run relationship exist among the variables in a model. The series do not necessarily require pre-testing of unit roots and hence the order of cointegration can be determined irrespective of their order integration (Pesaran & Shin, 1999). The critical value of the ARDL Bound testing depends on selected lag length; for this reason, the optimal lag (p) is determined empirically based on Akaike Information Criteria (AIC). The critical values reported in Pesaran, *et al.*, (2001) are equally adopted. Table 4.2 reports the result of the ARDL approach to co-integration.

Table 4.2 ARDL Bound Cointegration Test Result

Null Hypothesis: No Long-run Relationships Exist			
Model(s)	Test Statistic	Value	K
Model I	F-statistic	5.261486	6
	Critical Value Bounds		
	Significance	10 Bound	11 Bound
	10%	2.12	3.23
	5%	2.45	3.61
	2.5%	2.75	3.99
Model II	F-statistic	5.162818	6
	Critical Value Bounds		
	Significance	10 Bound	11 Bound
	10%	2.12	3.23
	5%	2.45	3.61
	2.5%	2.75	3.99
	1%	3.15	4.43

Source: Author's Compilation using E-views 13 Output

Among the advantages of the method is that it can be used to concomitantly estimate both the short-run and long-run effects of the independent variables on the explained variable, under small sample size. The outcome of ARDL model in Table 4.2 is subjected to a bound test with the aim of examining whether there is cointegration or not. The result of the bound tests reveals the rejection of the null of no cointegration for the models as indicated with F-statistics of 5.261486 and 5.162818 respectively, which are higher than the upper bound critical value at all the level of significance. Thus, the model shows that there

exists a long-run equilibrium relationship among the independent variables in the models used in the analysis. It shows that the variables move together in the long run. Therefore, financial technology (FinTech) has a long run sustainable impact of financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria. However, these variables might diverge from one another because of any shock to the Nigerian economy. Furthermore, the optimal lag length was determined using the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC). The AIC selected ARDL (1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) in the models was finally selected based on the AIC.

Akaike Information Criteria

Figure 4.1: Akaike Information Criterion Lag Length for Model One

Akaike Information Criteria

Figure 4.2: Akaike Information Criterion Lag Length for Model Two

4.3 ARDL Estimated Long-Run Coefficients

The findings for the long-run coefficient of the variables under investigation are estimated using the optimal ARDL model selection

according to the AIC criterion. The long-run and short-run and its corresponding coefficients of the model are given below based on research questions stated in chapter one.

4.3.1 Discussion of Results based on Research Objective One

To determine the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial service

delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Table 4.3 ARDLabridged estimated long-run and short-run coefficients based on ARDL (1, 0, 0, 0, 0) for model one.

Table 4.3 Estimated Long-run and short-run coefficients for model one

	Regressor	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Short-run	Log of Online Transactions D(LnOT)	7.058130	2.611607	2.702600	0.0256*
	Log of Point of Sale Transactions D(LnPOS)	4.756864	1.717746	2.769248	0.0206*
	Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions D(LnATM)	1.414918	0.701796	2.016139	0.0031*
	Log of Mobile Banking Transactions D(LnMBT)	0.509896	0.189375	2.692526	0.0064*
	Lending rate D(LR)	0.390534	0.100937	3.869067	0.0010*
	GDP Growth rate D(GDPG)	0.029679	0.017916	1.656551	0.3458
	CointEq(-1)	-1.818751	0.231492	-7.856661	0.0000*
	R-squared = 0.958037 Adjusted R-squared = 0.664294 F-statistics = 3.261486 Prob (F-statistics) = 0.002996 Durbin Watson = 2.690605				
Long-run	Log of Online Transactions (LnOT)	0.880757	0.395457	2.227188	0.0198*
	Log of Point of Sale Transactions (LnPOS)	2.615456	0.919589	2.844158	0.0152*
	Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions (LnATM)	0.777961	0.370220	2.101349	0.0428*
	Log of Mobile Banking Transactions (LnMBT)	0.280355	0.097271	2.882205	0.0126*

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Lending rate (LR)	0.214726	0.053944	3.980533	0.0067*
GDP Growth rate (GDPG)	0.016319	0.010044	1.624647	0.3513
Log of Deposit Money Banks Assets (LnDMBS) ie C	39.096511	13.139304	2.975539	0.2064

Source: Author's Compilation using E-views 13 Output

Note: * denote statistical significance at the 5% level.

For the time period under consideration, the coefficient of Online Transactions (LnOT) has a significant positive impact on the financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria, which translates to an increase in financial service delivery of deposit money banks of about 88.08% for every unit increase in LnOT while other variables remain constant. Customers can perform bank business conveniently through online/Internet banking from the comfort and security of their own homes and personal computers (Scott, 2017). Customers can now do transactions online that were previously limited to tellers within a bank branch. It is implied that the drop in teller transactions is due to Internet users' convenience in moving money, making deposits, and making withdrawal requests from their personal computers. Any firm can expand faster thanks to disruptive innovation, which also establishes a fresh trend in the marketplace. The findings of Ashiru, et al., (2023) and Muhammad, et al., (2022) are in agreement with this finding. Also, the coefficient of Point of Sale Transactions

(LnPOS) significantly improves the way Nigerian deposit money banks perform financial services. Hence, an increase in Point of Sale Transactions (LnPOS) will result in a 261.5% improvement in the financial service provided by deposit money institutions. POS banking is essentially used for efficient financial services. The inference is that, as indicated by Sylvester, Emmanuel, Obas, Andrew, and Abel, (2015) a weak network and high operating costs have continued to be major obstacles to the deployment of POS terminals. The findings of Ashiru, et al., (2023) and Muhammad, et al., (2022) are in agreement with this finding.

The supply of financial services by deposit money institutions in Nigeria is significantly improved by analysis of the long-run coefficients of automated teller machines (LnATM). This suggests that a long-term improvement of 77.8% will result from a 1% rise in LnATM in deposit money institutions in Nigeria. The market has been driven by the incredible expansion and development of technical advancement recently. The introduction of LnATM facilities has transformed the banking industry. To improve

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their performance and stifle competition, Nigerian banks are vigorously encouraging the issuance and use of LnATM cards, credit cards, debit cards, and smart cards. Also, the coefficient of Mobile Banking Transactions (LnMBT) significantly improves the way Nigerian deposit money banks provide financial services. This suggests that a 1% increase in LnMBT will, over time, boost the provision of financial services by deposit money banks in Nigeria by a factor of about 50.99%. The conclusion is that a variety of banking apps exist that assist users in comprehending and analysing their yearly, monthly, and even daily spending patterns. John (2017) also showed that, in order to stay current with their banking needs, an increasing number of banking users are using mobile banking applications. Supported by the theory of disruptive innovation, which shows how companies use new technologies to their advantage. The findings of Ashiru, et al., (2023) and Muhammad, et al., (2022) are in agreement with this finding. According to this, the coefficient of lending interest rate (LR) significantly enhances deposit money banks' ability to provide financial services in Nigeria. In a similar line, the delivery of financial services by Nigeria's deposit money banks is positively impacted by the gross domestic product growth rate (GDPG), however this effect is negligible. This suggests that over time, a 1% rise in LR and GDPG will enhance the delivery of financial services by deposit money

banks in Nigeria by 21.47% and 1.63%, respectively.

The short-run coefficient showed strong positive impact on financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria from online transactions D (LnOT), point of sale transactions D (LnPOS), ATM transactions D (LnATM), mobile banking transactions D (LnMBT), and lending rate D (LnLR). According to this, the coefficient of lending interest rate D (LR) has a negligible and minor impact on deposit money banks in Nigeria's ability to provide financial services. The delivery of financial services by Nigerian deposit money banks is similarly positively but marginally impacted by the coefficient of gross domestic product growth rate D (GDPG). This suggests that a 1% rise in D (LnOT), D (LnPOS), D (LnATM), D (LnMBT), D (LR), and D (GDPG) will, respectively, improve the delivery of financial services by Nigeria's deposit money banks by 705.8%, 475% 141%, 50.98%, 39.05%, and 2.96% in the short term.

However, the research found that the robust R-square, which denotes stronger goodness of fit, is 0.958037, indicating that the explanatory variables jointly accounted for 95.8% of the total variations in the financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The adjusted R² of 0.664294 demonstrated that, after removing the influence of the explanatory factors, the dependant variable is still explained by the equation with 66.4%, despite the adjusted (R²) tending to purge the influence of the number of included explanatory variables.

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Unsurprisingly, even after accounting for the degree of freedom, the regression's goodness of fit remained moderately high. However, the autoregressive process, an effective method for addressing this issue, has removed the autocorrelation problem. The overall significance level of the estimate was shown to be significant by the F-statistics, which were 3.261486 with a p-value of 0.002996. To determine whether there was any autocorrelation in the residuals (prediction errors) from a regression analysis, the Durbin Watson test was performed in the study. The aim of this test, however, is to prevent biased results because autocorrelation can lead to an underestimate of the standard error of the coefficient and makes the predictors appear important when they are not. The value of the Durbin Watson estimate, 2.690605, or 2, indicates that there was no autocorrelation in the relevant variable.

The ECMt-1 or CointEq(-1) coefficient demonstrates the rates of change from the short run to the long run equilibrium route. Correction of short-run to long-run discrepancies would be greater if adjustment speed were to increase (Banerjee, et al., 1993). Additionally, Bannerjee, et al., (1998) make the point that the statistical significance of the

error correction term allows us to confirm the long-term relationships between the variables that we have already established. The CointEq(-1) is significant and negative in the model, which is interesting. This suggests that our model is moving closer to achieving long-run equilibrium. Moreover, the ECM (-1)'s coefficient of error correction is -1.818751 and correctly signed. This rate of adjustment shows that the explanatory factors correct roughly 181.88% of the economic growth value's disequilibrium from the previous period each year. The implication is that any disequilibrium in the economic growth value will require approximately one year and two months to be adjusted by explanatory variables. Comparing the speed of adjustment to the relative adjustment, the speed of adjustment exhibits a very significant convergence towards the system's equilibrium period. This suggests that a somewhat high amount of adjustment is needed to return to long-run equilibrium.

4.3.2 Discussion of Results based on Research Objective Two

To examine the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial development in Nigeria, the table 4.4 ARDL abridged estimated long-run and short-run coefficients based on ARDL (1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0) for model two.

Table 4.4 Estimated Long-run and Short-run Coefficients for Model Two

	Regressor	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.	
Short-run	Log of Online Transactions D(LnOT)	1.061197	0.461549	2.299208	0.0018*	
	Log of Point of Sale Transactions D(LnPOS)	0.827124	0.402996	2.052437	0.0056*	
	Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions D(LnATM)	0.532378	0.836214	3.908394	0.0008*	
	Log of Mobile Banking Transactions D(LnMBT)	-0.199549	0.082450	2.420242	0.0036*	
	Lending rate D(LR)	1.036136	2.402651	0.431247	0.7408	
	GDP Growth rate D(GDPG)	-0.347782	0.291787	-1.191902	0.4444	
	CointEq(-1)	-1.335296	0.543969	-2.454728	0.0052*	
	R-squared = 0.938041 Adjusted R-squared = 0.504329 F-statistics = 5.162818 Prob (F-statistics) = 0.000629 Durbin Watson = 2.812141					
	Long-run	Log of Online Transactions (LnOT)	0.283703	0.057328	4.948768	0.0000*
Log of Point of Sale Transactions (LnPOS)		0.610611	0.217356	2.809266	0.0048*	
Log of Automated Teller Machine Transactions (LnATM)		0.398697	0.183107	2.177399	0.0103*	

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Log of Mobile Banking Transactions (LnMBT)	0.549442	0.166605	3.297872	0.0001*
Lending rate (LR)	0.775960	1.167883	0.664416	0.6267
GDP Growth rate (GDPG)	-0.260453	0.770528	-0.338019	0.7925
Private sector credit (PSC) ie C	48.753385	896.080264	0.054407	0.9654

Source: Author's Compilation using E-views 13 Output

Note: * denote statistical significance at the 5% level.

According to the regression analysis's findings, the coefficient of online transactions (LnOT) has a positive and significant influence on Nigeria's financial development. The aforementioned result makes it evident that a 1% increase in (LnOT) is associated with an improvement in Nigeria's financial development of 28.37%. The introduction of online banking as a financial technology to simplify banking transactions is anticipated to have had a favourable effect on the advancement of the financial system. The suspicion in this situation is that the country's poor internet connection and high data purchase costs may have hampered progress and discouraged individuals from using this medium (Moddibbo, 2019). The coefficient has a major beneficial impact on the financial development of Nigeria due to the function that Point of Sale (LnPOS) plays in the economy. According to this conclusion, a unit increase in LnPOS will, on average, improve Nigeria's financial development by 82.7% while holding

other variables constant. Lately, Point of Sale has developed into a common tool that both individuals and businesses use to do transactions without physically visiting a bank. This change facilitates corporate operations and job growth in the nation.

Nonetheless, the outcome of the regression demonstrates that the coefficient of Automatic Teller Machine Transactions (LnATM) has a very beneficial impact on the growth of Nigeria's financial sector. The aforementioned finding makes it evident that a 1% increase in real LnATM is associated with an improvement in Nigeria's financial development of around 39.87%. Due to its accessibility in rural areas and capacity to distribute all denominations in naira, it was able to have the anticipated impact. Also, there was a positive and substantial correlation between Nigeria's financial development and the coefficient of mobile banking transactions (LnMBT). This suggests that a 54.9% rise in Nigeria's financial development will result from an improvement in mobile banking transactions (LnMBT). This implied that banks with widespread acceptance

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of mobile banking are more likely to see rapid financial development than banks with smaller adoption rates. The lending rate (LR) coefficient has a positive but negligible impact on Nigeria's financial development for the control variables. This result implies, however, that a unit rise in the loan rate will, on average, promote financial development in Nigeria by roughly 77.6%, holding other variables constant. Once more, the GDP growth rate (GDPG) has little negative effects on Nigeria's financial development. The aforementioned finding makes it clear that a 1% rise in GDP growth rate is associated with a 26% decline in Nigeria's financial development.

The coefficient of Point of Sale Transactions D (LnPOS), Automated Teller Machine Transactions D (LnATM), and Online Transactions D (LnOT) has a positive and significant impact on financial development in Nigeria in the short term. The coefficient of Lending Rate D (LR) has a negligible positive effect on Nigeria's financial development. According to this, an increase of 1% in D (LnOT), D (LnPOS), D (LnATM), and D (LR) will each improve financial development in the near term by 106%, 82.7%, 53.2%, and 103.6%, respectively. The D (LnMBT) coefficient for mobile banking transactions has a negative but significant effect on Nigeria's financial development. In a similar vein, Nigeria's financial development is negatively and insignificantly impacted by the GDP growth rate D (GDPG). The aforementioned finding makes it abundantly evident that a 1% increase

in GDP growth rate and Mobile Banking Transactions is associated with a 19.95% and 34.78% reduction in Nigeria's financial development, respectively.

The coefficient of determination, however, is a summary metric that shows how well the sample regression line matches the data (R^2). R^2 for the third model from the top is 0.938041. This means that after removing the impacts of the explanatory factors, the dependent variable is still 93.8% explained by the equation, and the remaining 6.2% was explained by variables outside the model. The modified R^2 continues to explain 0.504329 (50.4%) of the variation in the dependent variable even when additional regressors are included. The regression has a low goodness of fit after taking the degree of freedom into consideration. The f-statistics of 5.162818, which reflects the cumulative significance of the explanatory factors, is determined to be statistically significant at the 1% level based on the related probability value of 0.000629. This demonstrates how well the model fits the data and that some variables are not significant. The model's value for Durbin Watson is 2.812141. The dependent variable and the predictor factors do not, therefore, exhibit any autocorrelation in Nigeria. The Error Correction Model displays a highly significant negative result. It can be shown from the CointEq(-1) coefficient that the model has a self-adjusting mechanism for balancing the short-run dynamics of the variables with their long-run values. The rate of adjustment to

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equilibrium is indicated as -1.335296 by the coefficient of $CointEq(-1)$. An out-of-equilibrium inflationary divergence may be corrected by as much as 133.5% the next year, according to this rate of change, which is extremely quick. According to Bannerjee, Dolado, and Mestre (1998) and Afolabi and Oluyemi (1995), "a highly considerable lagged $CointEq(-1)$ provides further indication of the presence of a stable long-run connection". This shows that some degree of modification is necessary to achieve long-term equilibrium.

4.3.3 Sensitivity Analysis

While developing and estimating a model, some diagnostic tests should be carried out (Davidson & Mackinnon, 1999). The ARDL bound test that was previously computed underwent additional testing for serial correlation, Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (ARCH), residual normality, functional form misspecification, and heteroskedasticity. Table 4.5 below contains the test results.

Table 4.5: Diagnostics Test Result for the Respective Models

Model(s)	Names of Tests	F –Statistic [p-value]
Model 1	Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	4.293225 [0.2863]
	Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.448252 [0.8211]
	ARCH Test	0.020900 [0.8898]
	Ramsey Reset Test	0.814607 [0.5326]
	Normality Test	0.906075 [0.635694]
Model 2	Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	5.759771 [0.2513]
	Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.853596 [0.6850]
	ARCH Test	0.592101 [0.4708]
	Ramsey Reset Test	2.061030 [0.3873]
	Normality Test	0.511729 [0.774247]

Source: Author's Compilation Using E-views 9 Output

The diagnostic tests revealed that the model has no issues with serial correlation, no ARCH effects, and hence no series volatility. The

residual is normally distributed, there is no heteroscedasticity issue, and there is no functional form misspecification in the model,

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all of which are demonstrated by the GARCH variance series. It may therefore be used as a measure of genuine volatility. This reassures us that the model results are accurate, dependable, and acceptable for forecasting, policy, and decision-making.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the impact of financial technology (FinTech) on financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria from 2012 to 2024. In order to determine the long run and short run, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was used. Prior to using the ARDL model, the Argument Dickey Fuller (ADF) unit root test was used to determine the stationary qualities of each variable of interest. Additional diagnostic tests were then performed to ensure the accuracy of the findings. However, it can be said that financial technology (FinTech) has a significant positive impact on the way deposit money banks in Nigeria deliver financial services. Also, financial technology (FinTech) has a significant impact on Nigeria's financial development. Consequently, adoption of FinTech services that have a cost-benefits approach will improve efficiency and social structure of FinTech enterprises in a more secure network, helping Nigerian Deposit Money Banks perform better and stay competitive. As a result, the study suggests, among other things:

1. The study suggests that management of banks should focus more on enhancing benefits associated with mobile, internet, and point of

sale transactions by providing more convenience to users in terms of user friendliness, fast network, payment methods, etc., given that financial technology (FinTech) has a significant positive impact on financial service delivery of deposit money banks in Nigeria. Increasing the variety of items available to customers can also boost their view of the advantages of mobile banking. Once more, management of the Nigerian Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) should immediately conduct regulatory network on the managerial practice on FinTech services and align them in order to ensure that banks do not lose market share and clients due to risks and challenges in the efficiency and security challenges in social networks of the FinTech services.

2. Financial technology (FinTech) has significant impact on Nigeria's financial development. Therefore, the study suggests that financial sector officials and practitioners try to increase their FinTech, since this would help to advance financial development. The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and other authorities should foster an atmosphere where banks can engage in financial technology initiatives. Although this will result in higher levels of financial development, the management and directors of commercial banks in Nigeria should make sure that customers may transact through all of their platforms without security issues. To make this a reality, the government should seek to expand internet access.

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